

***Trichomalopsis apanteloctena* (Crawford)**
[Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae]: correct name for the larval parasite of the rice skipper

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Eupteromalus parnarae Gahan is an important larval parasite of rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* (F.), leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenie), leaf beetle *Oulema oryzae* (Kuwayama), and whorl maggot *Hydrellia griseola* (Fallen) in

South and Southeast Asia. It is also a recorded hyperparasite of *Apanteles rificrus* Haliday on *Naranga aenescens* Moore, *A. parnarae* Watanabe and *A. booris* Wilkinson on *Parnara guttata* Bremer & Grey, *A. chilonis* Munakata on *Chilo suppressalis* (Wlk.), *A. plutellae* Kurdjumov on *Plutella xylostella* (L.), *Apanteles* sp. on *Grapholitha molesta* Busck., and *Meteorus* sp. on *Sesamium inferens* (Wlk.). Recent examination, however, indicates that specimens of the three known species of *Trichomalopsis* Crawford [May] 1913, *Eupteromalus*

Kurdjumov [Jul] 1913 became synonymized with *Trichomalopsis* following the rule of priority in zoological nomenclature. In the same manner, *E. parnarae* Gahan and *T. apanteloctena* Crawford were discovered to be one species (ref. Kamijo, K. and E. E. Grisell. 1982. Species of *Trichomalopsis* Crawford [Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae] from Rice Paddy, with descriptions of Two New Species. Kontyu 50 (1): 76-87). Therefore, the correct name for *E. parnarae* Gahan is *Trichomalopsis apanteloctena* (Crawford). □

Effect of some granular insecticides on rice gall midge

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The effectiveness of seven granular insecticides to control rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) was evaluated at Raipur. Quinalphos 5G, phorate 10G, mephosfolan 5G, diazinon 10G, carbaryl + γ -BHC (Sevidol 4G), chlorpyrifos 5G, and carbofuran 3G were applied at 1.0 kg ai/ha during the 1980 wet season. Chemicals were applied 3 times at 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Two-three seedlings/hill were planted in 4 × 6-m plots at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Each plot was divided into 4 subplots, and 9 hills/subplot were

Effect of granular insecticides on rice gall midge infestation and rice yield. Raipur, India, 1980 wet season.^a

Treatment	Silvershoots (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	30 DT	50 DT	70 DT	
Phorate	6.8 a	9.2 b	8.5 c	1.6 a
Chlorpyrifos	6.5 a	4.5 a	2.4 a	1.5 ab
Diazinon	4.8 a	11.9 c	12.3 d	1.5 ab
Mephosfolan	3.0 a	9.1 b	5.6 b	1.3 ab
Carbaryl + Lindane	4.8 a	11.2 c	11.2 c	1.0 ab
Carbofuran	5.6 a	9.6 b	10.8 c	0.9 b
Quinalphos	4.6 a	15.8 e	18.6 f	0.9 b
Untreated	4.1 a	14.2 d	16.2 a	0.3 b

^aDT = days after transplanting. Figures with similar letters do not differ significantly.

examined 10 days after each application for damaged tillers and silvershoots. At 30 DT GM incidence was low and uneven; therefore, differences among treatments after the first application were insignificant (see table). GM incidence increased by 40 DT. Percentage of affected tillers was significantly lower for chlorpyrifos than for the control. Other treatments

were similar to the control. Chlorpyrifos also controlled GM best at 60 DT. Mephosfolan, phorate, and carbofuran also reduced damage.

Only the phorate treatment yielded significantly more (1.6 t/ha) than the untreated control (0.3 t/ha) but chlorpyrifos, diazinon, and mephosfolan treatments also yielded slightly more. □

A leaf dipping method for testing insecticide toxicity

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is a serious rice pest in southwestern Japan. Insecticide toxicity to the larvae was laboratory tested by leaf dipping. Adult moths, which were collected from fields in mid-Oct 1980, oviposited inside a glass jar. They were fed rice seedlings after hatching. Leaf blades of 12- to

LC₅₀ values of insecticides to rice leaffolder larvae using the leaf dipping method.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (ppm) at 25°C					
	1st instar		3d instar		5th instar	
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h	24 h	47 h
Cartap	1.2	0.70	2.0	1.3	8.2	6.4
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	2.1	1.9	7.8	7.2	31	21
Dimethylvinphos	4.3	3.7	17	15	27	16
Tetrachlorvinphos	11	9.5	26	22	34	21

15-cm-high plants at tillering stage were dipped for 10 s into 100-ml insecticide solutions diluted with methanol, then air-dried for 5 min. The roots were wrapped

in moist paper. Larvae were released on treated rice seedlings in 3 × 20-cm test tubes in a growth chamber kept at 25°C and 16 L. Larval mortality was recorded